

more than the local modern improved variety Nanjing 11 and hybrid Nanyou 6.

BG90-2 has high, stable BB resistance, and is a source of BB resistance in breed-

ing programs. It is one of 12 best resistant sources among 10,688 accessions screened by the Plant Protection Institute of the Guangdong Provincial Academy of

Agricultural Sciences. BG90-2 also has good morphoagronomic characters (see table). □

New sources of resistance to major rice diseases

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We evaluated 46 rice varieties at TNAU, Coimbatore, for reaction to brown spot (BS), bacterial blight (BB), and sheath rot (ShR) under artificial screening conditions using the Standard Evaluation

System for Rice. AS18699 and AS19703 had multiple disease resistance (see table). □

Reaction of rice varieties to BS, BB, and ShR, Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a		
	BS	BB	ShR (% infection)
AS688	5	5	2
AS6520	3	3	10
AS18696	5	3	NT
AS18699	3	3	9
AS19103	3	3	2
AS19789	5	5	4
AS19903	5	3	NT
AS22954	3	5	NT
AS23598	5	3	15
AS23972	3	5	7

^a 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible; NT = not tested.

Reaction of IR varieties to rice yellow dwarf (RYD)

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Reactions of 26 IR varieties to RYD infection were tested in the greenhouse. Newly emerged *Nephotettix virescens* nymphs had 25-d acquisition access on RYD-infected TN1 plants. Six-day-old seedlings were confined with 2 viruliferous insects per seedling in test tubes for 1 d. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted in clay pots, kept in screened trays, and scored 40-60 d after inoculation. Percentage infection of IR varieties was 20-76%. TN1 was 97% infected. Six IR varieties had RYD infection lower than 30% and were considered resistant (see table). □

Reaction of ASD varieties to various rice diseases

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In 1983-84, 15 rice varieties released by the Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamudram, were screened for disease resistance by artificial inoculation in the greenhouse at TNAU. Varieties were evaluated for resistance to brown spot (BS), bacterial blight (BB), sheath rot (ShR), blast (BI), and rice tungro virus (RTV) using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES). ASD5 and ASD11 had multiple disease resistance (see table). □

Disease resistance of ASD varieties, Coimbatore, India.^a

Variety	Disease rating ^a				
	BI	BS	BB	RTV	ShR
ASD1	3	5	5	5	5
ASD2	3	5	5	5	3
ASD3	3	5	7	5	3
ASD4	5	5	7	5	3
ASD5	3	3	3	1	3
ASD6	3	5	3	5	3
ASD7	5	3	5	5	3
ASD8	5	5	5	5	5
ASD9	5	3	5	3	3
ASD10	5	5	5	3	5
ASD11	3	3	3	3	3
ASD12	3	5	5	3	3
ASD13	NT	3	3	NT	NT
ASD14	7	3	5	3	5
ASD15	7	5	7	5	5

^a By the 1980 SES scale: 0-3 = resistant, 5 = moderate, 7 = susceptible, 9 = highly susceptible, NT = not tested.

IR varieties with low percentages of RYD infection, IIRRI, 1984.

Variety	Total tested ^a (no.)	Plants infected (%)
IR7	108	20
IR24	104	24
IR26	102	24
IR29	104	25
IR30	100	27
IR43	107	21
TN1 (check)	95	97

^a Based on 6 trials, each involving 20 seedlings/variety.

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

INSECT RESISTANCE

Behavior of two green leafhopper (GLH) colonies on three rice varieties

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We sought to determine if selection of a GLH *Nephotettix virescens* biotype on a variety with a major gene for resistance results in cross adaptation to another variety with the same major resistance gene.

The response of two GLH colonies—one from susceptible TN1 and selected on moderately resistant TAPL #796 for 18 generations, and another reared on TN1 for at least 100 generations—was determined based on survival, develop-